

The complexes were prepared by mixing the reactants keeping a little excess of succinimide over the calculated amount in order to get the 1 : 2 (M : L) complexes and adjusting the $pH \approx 7.0$, 5.0 and 5.0 in the case of Pd(II), Th(IV) and Ce(IV) respectively with KOH. The resulting solutions were concentrated by slow evaporation at a temperature $\approx 65^\circ$ in a thermostat until the precipitates were formed, which were filtered off, washed several times with 50% alcohol and then dried over anhydrous sulfuric acid. However the complexes of Au(III) and Pd(IV) could not be isolated in the solid form.

(i) Found : Pd, 31.40% ; C, 28.40% ; H, 3.49%
Calc. for $[Pd(C_4H_4O_2N)_2(H_2O)_2]$: Pd, 31.44% ; C, 28.36% ; H, 3.54%.

(ii) Found : Ce, 37.50% ; C, 25.82% ; H, 2.60%
Calc. for $[Ce(C_4H_4O_2N)_2(OH)_2]$: Ce, 37.65% ; C, 25.79% ; H, 2.69%.

(iii) Found : Th, 50.18% ; C, 20.82% ; H, 2.10%
Calc. for $[Th(C_4H_4O_2N)_2(OH)_2]$: Th, 50.21% ; C, 20.77% ; H, 2.16%.

Palladium complex, on treatment with ammonia, or aliphatic amine gave white coloured crystalline complexes. The chemical analysis for the palladium carbon and hydrogen favoured the formulae of the type $[Pd(C_4H_4O_2N)_2(A)_2]$ where A=ammonia, methyl amine, ethyl amine, isopropyl amine or iso-butyl amine.

All these complexes were diamagnetic and of nonelectrolytic nature in nitrobenzene.

Results and Discussion

The pH titrations of the mixture of metal ion and succinimide in the ratios 1 : 0, 1 : 1, 1 : 2, and 1 : 3 with 0.1M KOH indicated a downward shift in pH from 1 : 0 to 1 : 1 in the case of Au(III) and Pt(IV) and from 1 : 0 to 1 : 1 to 1 : 2 in the case of other metals showing the liberation of hydrogen ions during the complex ion formation. Blank titration with succinimide had no effect upon the titration curves described above.

pK values as determined by potentiometric titration of 40 ml succinimide (0.025M) vs 0.084 KOH were found 9.45 and 9.70 in KCl and KNO_3 medium of 0.1M respectively.

Stability constants at $20^\circ \pm 1^\circ$ and keeping the ion strength constant at 0.1 with KCl, in case of Pd(II), Au(III) and Pt(IV) and with KNO_3 in case of Ce(IV) and Th(IV) were determined by Bjerrum's method⁶. The value of $\log K$ (concentration constant) was found to be 17.4 ($\log k_1=9.1$, $\log k_2=8.3$), 18.9 ($\log k_1=10.2$, $\log k_2=8.7$), 14.6 ($\log k_1=7.5$, $\log k_2=7.1$), 6.2 and 8.4 in case of Pd(II), Ce(IV), Th(IV), Au(III) and Pt(IV) respectively. The accuracy of $\log K$ reported was 0.02. The \bar{n} values beyond ≈ 2.0 in case of Pd(II), Ce(IV) and Th(IV) and ≈ 1.0 in case of Au(III) and Pt(IV) could not be obtained with accuracy due to the onset of hydrolysis. The presence of polynuclear species could be neglected since the formation curves

(\bar{n} vs pA) determined from the ligand metal ratio of 5 : 1 and 6 : 1 were found identical.

The combining ratio was further confirmed by conductometric titration (20 ml of the ligand of conc. 0.03M and 0.05M in the cell) and amperometric titrations carried out at the plateau of succinimide i.e. -0.75 V. The main characteristic feature of the i.r spectra were the same as reported earlier⁵ with the difference of the bands associated with coordinated hydroxo group (1030 cm^{-1} and 600 cm^{-1}) and water molecules (820 cm^{-1} and 660 cm^{-1}).

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Preparation of (\pm)-Nitriles and (\pm)-Amides of Propesine and Butesine as Potential Drugs

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PROPESINE and butesine are known for their local anesthetic activity^{1,2}. They are also reported as antibacterial and antitubercular compounds^{3,4}. (\pm)- α -Aminonitriles are reported as compounds possessing insecticidal as well as CNS stimulant property^{5,6}.

In continuation of our previous work*, we prepared (\pm) nitriles of propesine and butesine as drug potentials for testing their antibacterial activity.

The (\pm) - α -Aminonitriles of the type.

have been synthesised, where

$\text{R}' = n - \text{C}_3\text{H}_7$ or $n - \text{C}_4\text{H}_9$ and

$\text{R} = \text{C}_6\text{H}_5$; 4- $\text{CH}_3\text{O} \cdot \text{C}_6\text{H}_4$; 3- $\text{NO}_2 \cdot \text{C}_6\text{H}_4$; $\text{C}_4\text{H}_9\text{O}$; 3- $\text{CH}_3\text{O} - 4 - \text{HO} \cdot \text{C}_6\text{H}_3$; 5- $\text{O}_2\text{N} - 3 - \text{CH}_3\text{O} - 4 - \text{HO} \cdot \text{C}_6\text{H}_2$; 3,4- $(\text{CH}_3\text{O})_2 \cdot \text{C}_6\text{H}_3$; 6-Br - 3,4- $(\text{CH}_3\text{O})_2 \cdot \text{C}_6\text{H}_2$; $\text{C}_6\text{H}_5\text{CH}=\text{CH}$; etc.

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The compounds of the type (I) are treated with excess of concentrated H₂SO₄ at 0° and allowed to stand for 48 hr. at room temp. to get the (±)-amides⁷ of the type,

where R and R' are same as above, to study their physiological activity⁸⁻¹⁰.

The (±)-nitriles were tested by N-agar pour plate method for their antibacterial activity against *E. coli*, *S. albus*, pathogen pseudomonas pyrorubora pigments (brown pigment producing). The solvent used, which also worked as control, was ether. At the concentration of 100 μg compounds No. 2,4,5,6,7,8,10 (Table I)

of the cases but in some cases it was separated when the reaction mixture was poured on ice and crystallised from ethanol. The physical and analytical data are reported in Table 1.

Hydrolysis of the (±)-α-aminonitriles to (±)-amides (II): The (±) nitrile was treated with excess of conc. H₂SO₄ at 0° and then was allowed to stand for 48 hrs. at room temperature. The resulted (±)-amide was separated by diluting the reaction mixture with ice-water. The product was filtered, dried and crystallised from ethanol. The physical and analytical data are reported in Table 2.

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TABLE 1—COMPOUNDS OF THE TYPE (I)

Sr. No.	R	R'	Molecular Formula	M.P. °C	Calcd. % N	Found % N
1.	C ₂ H ₅	n-C ₃ H ₇	C ₁₈ H ₁₈ N ₂ O ₃	94	9.41	9.53
2.	4-CH ₃ O.C ₆ H ₄	n-C ₃ H ₇	C ₁₂ H ₂₀ N ₂ O ₃	64	8.49	8.64
3.	C ₄ H ₉ O	n-C ₄ H ₉	C ₁₇ H ₁₈ N ₂ O ₃	100	9.08	9.40
4.	3-CH ₃ O-4-HO.C ₆ H ₃	n-C ₃ H ₇	C ₁₉ H ₂₀ N ₂ O ₄	135	8.12	8.24
5.	3-CH ₃ O-4-HO.C ₆ H ₃	n-C ₄ H ₉	C ₂₀ H ₂₁ N ₂ O ₄	142	7.63	7.85
6.	5-O ₂ N-3-CH ₃ O-4-HO.C ₆ H ₃	n-C ₃ H ₇	C ₁₉ H ₁₉ N ₃ O ₆	108	11.05	10.91
7.	3,4-(CH ₃ O) ₂ .C ₆ H ₃	n-C ₃ H ₇	C ₂₀ H ₂₃ N ₂ O ₄	106	7.65	7.89
8.	3,4-(CH ₃ O) ₂ .C ₆ H ₃	n-C ₄ H ₉	C ₂₁ H ₂₄ N ₂ O ₄	92	7.37	7.71
9.	6-Br-3,4-(CH ₃ O) ₂ .C ₆ H ₃	n-C ₃ H ₇	C ₂₀ H ₂₁ BrN ₂ O ₄	100	6.24	6.47
10.	6-Br-3,4-(CH ₃ O) ₂ .C ₆ H ₃	n-C ₄ H ₉	C ₂₁ H ₂₃ BrN ₂ O ₄	138	6.48	6.27
11.	C ₆ H ₅ CH=CH	n-C ₄ H ₉	C ₂₁ H ₂₃ N ₂ O ₃	116	8.18	8.39

TABLE 2—COMPOUNDS OF THE TYPE (II)

Sr. No.	R	R'	Molecular formula	M.P. (°C)	Calcd. % N	Found %N
1.	C ₂ H ₅	n-C ₃ H ₇	C ₁₈ H ₂₀ N ₂ O ₃	143	8.76	8.97
2.	4-CH ₃ O.C ₆ H ₄	n-C ₃ H ₇	C ₁₂ H ₂₂ N ₂ O ₃	198	8.32	8.19
3.	3-CH ₃ O-4-HO.C ₆ H ₃	n-C ₃ H ₇	C ₁₉ H ₂₂ N ₂ O ₅	195	7.66	7.82
4.	3-CH ₃ O-4-HO.C ₆ H ₃	n-C ₄ H ₉	C ₂₀ H ₂₄ N ₂ O ₅	180 (d)	7.42	7.53
5.	3,4-(CH ₃ O) ₂ .C ₆ H ₃	n-C ₃ H ₇	C ₂₀ H ₂₄ N ₂ O ₅	84 (d)	7.36	7.51
6.	3,4-(CH ₃ O) ₂ .C ₆ H ₃	n-C ₄ H ₉	C ₂₁ H ₂₆ N ₂ O ₅	172(d)	7.41	7.24
7.	5-O ₂ N-3-CH ₃ O-4-HO.C ₆ H ₃	n C ₃ H ₇	C ₁₉ H ₂₁ N ₃ O ₇	118 (d)	10.23	10.24

and control showed no antibacterial effect on any of the three bacterial species, at this particular concentration.

Experimental

Preparation of (±)-nitriles of propesine and butesine¹¹ (I): The aldehyde (0.1 mole) was dissolved in ethanol (95%) or methanol (40 ml) and potassium cyanide (0.1 mole) in water (10 ml) was added, followed by glacial acetic acid (0.1 mole). The mixture stirred mechanically and the amine ((0.1 mole) dissolved in ethanol (95%) or methanol (70 ml) was added. The reaction mixture was allowed to stand for 24 hr. at 25°-30°. The product separated as crystals in most

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Synthesis and Ion Exchange Properties of New Series of Inorganic Ion Exchangers : VII Hydrous Cerium (IV), Oxide and Thorium Antimonate.

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IN continuation of our work on the development of new inorganic ion exchangers¹⁻⁶, we have found hydrous cerium (IV) oxide and thorium antimonate to have useful ion exchange properties. These belong to the classes of hydrous oxides of metals and insoluble salts of polybasic metals respectively⁷. The present communication summarises our preliminary studies on these inorganic ion exchangers.

Experimental

Reagents: All the chemicals used were of analar grade (B.D.H. or S. Merck).

Apparatus: pH measurements were made with an Elico Model 10 pH meter, Hyderabad, India Spectromom 2.2 (Hungary) was used for spectrophotometric work.

Synthesis: Hydrous cerium (IV) oxide of two different forms were prepared by mixing ceric sulfate and sodium hydroxide solutions in different ratios at room temperature. Crystalline variety was obtained using the normal order of addition of the reagents (ceric sulphate/sodium hydroxide) while amorphous form was obtained by reversing the order of addition (sodium hydroxide/ceric sulphate). In each case the mixture was digested for 2 hr. at room temperature.

Thorium antimonate was prepared by mixing thorium nitrate and potassium pyroantimonate solutions in nitric acid and also by mixing thorium nitrate and antimony pentachloride solutions in different ratios at room temperature. The mixture was digested for 2 hr. at room temperature.

Results and Discussion

The compositions of both hydrous cerium (IV) dioxide and thorium antimonate were established by analysis by standard methods. The former had CeO₂ : H₂O ratios 2.58 (crystalline) and 3.00 (amorphous) while the latter had Sb. The ratios 3.67, 4.27 etc. These products are fairly stable in acids of moderate concentrations (upto 0.5 M) and more stable in water and alkali at room temperature.

pH titration curves were obtained by following the method of Topp and Peppers⁸ by shaking intermittently a known weight of the exchanger with different amounts of alkali, MoH (M=Li, Na or K) plus alkali sulphate. The curves indicate monofunctional behaviour of the exchangers. The ion exchange capacities of the exchangers at different pH were determined from the pH titrations. The ion exchange capacities follow the sequence: Li⁺ < Na⁺ < K⁺ < NH₄⁺, which agree with the order of decreasing hydrated ionic radius in the series. With increase in pH, there is increase in the ion exchange capacity values.

Distribution coefficient values of various metal ions were measured at optimum pH 6-8 as reported in our earlier papers¹⁻⁶ and on the basis of these values several selective ion exchange separation schemes have been worked out. Details of these investigations will be published elsewhere.

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Copper Thiomalate as an Indicator in the Volumetric Estimation of Rare Earths

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RECENTLY¹ it was reported that copper-thiomalate can be effectively used as an indicator in the volumetric estimation of Al(III), Ga(III) and In(III). The same metal indicator can be successfully employed in